

~~ASAP~~

EVERY KID KNOWS

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WHAT IS “EVERY KID KNOWS”?

"Every Kid Knows" is a set of key ideas and questions that help explain what the ASAP Educational Programme is all about.

It's inspired by Gregory Bateson's idea that some things should be so clear and important that "every schoolboy knows" them. So, we made sure the language is simple, friendly, and easy for every kid (and every adult!) to understand.

"Every Kid Knows" helps explore how preadolescents grow – in their brains, bodies, emotions, and relationships – and how social and digital media affect how they think, feel, and behave. It also supports learning how to listen and communicate better, manage emotions, think critically, and make smart choices online.

It's designed to help preadolescents understand themselves during this important time of change, and to help adults support them as they grow, connect with others, and explore the world around them.

These ideas are shared as cards so everyone can access, use, and share them. Each message is framed as a question because asking good questions helps us think better, learn better, and understand more deeply.

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1. WHAT CHANGES HAPPEN IN THE BRAIN DURING PREADOLESCENCE?

During preadolescence, the brain is growing and changing in powerful ways. It goes through a clean-up process called synaptic pruning this means that the brain keeps the connections that are used often and removes the ones that aren't. At the same time, the brain is highly flexible—this is called neuroplasticity. It means the brain can strengthen and build new connections through learning, practice, and experiences. These changes help the brain become faster and more efficient.

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2. WHY DO PREADOLESCENTS SOMETIMES ACT WITHOUT THINKING CAREFULLY?

The frontal lobe of the brain, which helps with planning, decision-making, and self-control, is still developing during preadolescence. That means it's harder for preteens to pause and think things through before acting.

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3. WHY ARE EMOTIONS SO INTENSE DURING PREADOLESCENCE?

The amygdala, the part of the brain that controls emotions, is especially active during preadolescence. This can make emotions and feelings like anger, joy, or sadness feel very strong and hard to manage at times.

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4. WHY DO PREADOLESCENTS START THINKING ABOUT BIGGER, DEEPER TOPICS?

Preteens are beginning to develop abstract thinking. That means they can think about ideas like fairness, justice, the future, and “what if” questions, not just things they can see or touch.

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5. WHY DOES FITTING IN WITH FRIENDS BECOME SO IMPORTANT DURING PREADOLESCENCE?

The social brain becomes more active during this time. Preadolescents start to care more about what others think, seek acceptance from peers, and become more aware of social groups and dynamics. They're also beginning to build independence and autonomy from adults, so friends become a bigger part of how they see themselves and make decisions.

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6. HOW DOES MEMORY CHANGE DURING PREADOLESCENCE?

Both working memory, which holds short-term information, and long-term memory improve. This helps preteens learn, follow instructions, and handle more complex tasks.

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7. HOW DOES PUBERTY AFFECT THE BRAIN?

Hormones like oestrogen and testosterone begin to rise during puberty. These hormones affect brain development, causing shifts in mood, sleep patterns, energy, and how young people feel about themselves and others.

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8. WHY IS SLEEP SO IMPORTANT FOR PREADOLESCENTS?

Sleep helps the brain grow, organise memories, and process emotions. Preadolescents usually need about 9–11 hours of sleep each night to stay focused, calm, and healthy during the day. However, late-night screen time, especially scrolling through social media or watching videos, can trick the brain into staying awake longer. The light from screens can block melatonin, the “sleep hormone,” making it harder to fall asleep and get good rest.

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9. DO BOYS' AND GIRLS' BRAINS GROW THE SAME WAY?

Brain develops at different paces for everyone. Girls may mature earlier in areas like emotion and language, while boys may show growth in spatial and physical areas. These differences are small and normal, and they are part of neuroindividuality: every brain grows in its own way.

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10. WHY IS IT SO EASY TO SPEND A LOT OF TIME ON SOCIAL MEDIA?

Social media platforms can be addictive because they are designed to keep users engaged. Features like endless scrolling, likes, and notifications give the brain small rewards, releasing dopamine – a substance that makes us feel pleasure and pushes us to keep going. Preadolescents are especially vulnerable because the frontal lobe, the part of the brain that helps with self-control, is still developing. This makes it harder for them to stop once they've started.

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WHAT IS EMPATHY?

Empathy means being able to understand how someone else is feeling and seeing things from their point of view. It's like stepping into another person's shoes. Empathy helps people build strong, caring relationships and connect with others in a real and meaningful way.

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WHAT IS ACTIVE LISTENING?

Active listening means really paying attention to what someone is saying, not just hearing the words. It includes looking at the speaker, nodding or showing interest, not interrupting, and asking thoughtful questions. It also means checking that you've understood by repeating back what was said in your own words. Active listening helps people communicate better and builds trust and respect in relationships.

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WHAT IS ASSERTIVE BEHAVIOUR?

Being assertive means speaking up clearly and respectfully. It's about saying what you really think or feel without being rude or hurting others. Assertive behaviour shows confidence, protects personal boundaries, and helps people express their needs while still respecting others. It's important for building healthy self-esteem and strong relationships.

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WHAT IS DIGITAL EMPATHY?

Digital empathy means thinking about how someone else might feel before writing, commenting, or sharing something online. Behind every screen is a real person with real emotions. A post that seems funny to one person might really hurt someone else. Practising digital empathy helps keep online spaces kind and respectful.

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WHAT ARE THE CONSEQUENCES OF OUR WORDS ONLINE?

What someone writes, posts, or shares online can have a big impact. Unkind messages can hurt feelings, damage self-esteem, or cause long-lasting problems. Even if it's "just words," those words reach real people. That's why it's important to use language online with care and respect.

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WHY SHOULD PEOPLE PAUSE BEFORE POSTING ONLINE?

Strong emotions like anger or frustration can lead to quick, harmful posts. Taking a few seconds to pause and reflect can make a big difference. It helps to ask: “Is this kind?”, “Is this helpful?”, or “Would I be okay if someone I respect read this?” A short pause can prevent long-term harm.

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WHAT IS A DIGITAL FOOTPRINT?

A digital footprint is the record we leave online, like posts, searches, and comments. It can be seen by others and often lasts a long time. Being careful about what we share helps protect our privacy, reputation, and safety in the digital world.

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HOW CAN SOMEONE BE A RESPONSIBLE DIGITAL CITIZEN?

A responsible digital citizen uses technology in smart, respectful, and safe ways. This means protecting privacy, managing screen time, thinking before posting, and treating others kindly online. It's important because our actions online affect real people and shape the kind of internet we all live in.

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WHAT DOES IT MEAN TO LIVE IN AN “ONLIFE” WORLD?

“Onlife” means our online and offline lives are connected. What happens online can affect how we feel, think, and act in real life – and the other way around. Knowing this helps people make better choices and find a healthy balance with technology.

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CAN YOU TRUST WHAT YOU SEE ONLINE?

When seeing something online, it's important to ask, "How do I know this is true?" Check who wrote it and whether they are an expert. Also, notice if strong feelings like excitement, anger, or fear are making you believe it too quickly. Understanding emotions helps avoid being tricked by false information.

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WHAT TYPE OF INFORMATION IS THIS?

Information online can be facts, opinions, or entertainment. Facts can be checked and proven true. Opinions are personal ideas or feelings. Entertainment might be just for fun and not always true. Knowing the difference helps decide how much to trust and share what you find.

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COULD SOMEONE BE SPREADING MISINFORMATION, INCLUDING ME?

Before sharing something online, ask, “Is this true?”
Sharing false information can hurt others. Taking a
moment to check if the information is trustworthy
helps stop misinformation from spreading and
shows responsibility for what we share online.

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DO THE PEOPLE YOU LOOK UP TO SHARE VALUES YOU LIKE?

The people around us, both offline and online, share many kinds of values: kindness, respect, popularity, success and more. Thinking about what matters to us and choosing role models with values close to ours, who inspire us, can help us grow and be your best self.

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HOW DO OTHER PEOPLE, ONLINE AND OFFLINE, AFFECT HOW WE SEE OURSELVES?

What people show or say – on social media or in everyday life – can change how we see ourselves. Sometimes we see perfect photos or comments that make us feel that we are “not good enough”, even though they are not always true or don’t show the full story. Other times we find messages that make us feel heard and understood. Comparing both can help us choose what makes us feel good and who really supports us.

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BEFORE YOU JOIN A TREND, DO YOU CHECK IF IT'S SAFE AND RIGHT FOR YOU?

Some viral challenges seem fun but can be risky or not match what you believe. Someone we admire and trust can help us think for ourselves, say no if we don't feel like it – even when others push us – and ask: “Is this safe and right for me?”. Taking time to reflect before following a trend helps us choose what we believe is best for ourselves and keep safe.

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The ASAP project is co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043. The support of the European Commission and of the Italian National Agency INDIRE to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of its content, which reflects the views of the authors only. The European Commission and the Italian National Agency INDIRE shall not be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained herein.

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